

Postoperative circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) dynamics as an early indicator of molecular residual disease in lung cancer: preliminary results and correlation with TNM status, adjuvant therapy, and clinical outcome^{*}

Hristo Ivanov¹,
Antoaneta Chirlova-Kulenska²

¹ Department of Medical Genetics, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

² Department of Special Surgery, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Hristo Ivanov (doctorhristoivanov@yahoo.com)

Received 30 January 2026 ♦ Accepted 11 May 2026 ♦ Published 21 May 2026

Citation: Ivanov H, Stoyanova V, Linev A, Pochileev I, Chirlova-Kulenska A, Chapkanov A, Dimov R (2026) Postoperative circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) dynamics as an early indicator of molecular residual disease in lung cancer: preliminary results and correlation with TNM status, adjuvant therapy, and clinical outcome. *Pharmacia* 73: e187008. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e187008>

Abstract

Background: Recurrence after curative-intent surgery remains a major clinical challenge in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Conventional radiologic follow-up detects relapse only once macroscopic disease becomes evident, missing the minimal residual disease (MRD) window. Circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), a tumor-derived fraction of total circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA), has emerged as a sensitive biomarker for early MRD detection. This pilot study evaluates postoperative cfDNA dynamics as an accessible surrogate for MRD monitoring.

Methods: Twelve patients with histologically confirmed NSCLC undergoing curative-intent resection were prospectively monitored at four time points: preoperatively (T_0), postoperative day 10 (T_1), 1 month (T_2), and 3 months (T_3). Blood samples were collected in Streck Cell-Free DNA BCT[®] tubes and processed using a double-centrifugation protocol. cfDNA was extracted using the Maelstrom Switch 8 automated system and quantified fluorometrically. Longitudinal cfDNA trends were correlated with TNM stage, adjuvant therapy, and survival outcome. Welch's t -tests, ANOVA, and simple linear regression assessed associations between cfDNA levels and mortality.

Results: Most patients (10/12; 83.3%) demonstrated a steady postoperative decline in cfDNA, consistent with molecular clearance. Two patients (16.7%) exhibited persistent or rising cfDNA and were the only patients who died during follow-up. At T_3 , cfDNA levels were significantly higher in deceased vs. surviving patients (0.2821 vs. 0.2325 ng/ μ L, $p = 0.029$). Linear regression revealed a negative association between cfDNA at T_3 and survival probability ($\beta = -3.62$, $R^2 = 0.18$). Early postoperative cfDNA (T_1 – T_2) lacked prognostic value.

Conclusion: Persistently elevated cfDNA levels at 3 months post-surgery were observed in patients with unfavorable outcomes; however, variability between individual trajectories was also present. These findings suggest that postoperative cfDNA dynamics may reflect underlying biological processes related to minimal residual disease, but given the small cohort size, they should be interpreted as hypothesis-generating. Larger prospective studies integrating mutation-specific ctDNA assays and time-to-event analyses are required to validate the potential clinical utility of cfDNA-based postoperative monitoring.

^{*} This article is part of: "Science and technologies in biomedicine", edited by Svetlana Fotkova Georgieva, Georgi Momekov, Alexander Zlatkov, Yoana Kiselova-Kaneva, Lily Peikova, Emilio Mateev, Valentina Petkova, Ivanka Pencheva, Milen Dimitrov.

Keywords

Postoperative surveillance, minimal residual disease, cfDNA kinetics, lung cancer

Introduction

Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related mortality globally, accounting for approximately 18% of all cancer deaths (Pu et al. 2025). Although advances in early detection and surgical techniques have improved outcomes, recurrence after curative-intent surgery remains a major challenge. For example, in patients with early-stage non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC, stages I–III) who undergo complete resection, the recurrence rate has been reported in the range of 30–55% within two years (Pu et al. 2025). This high relapse risk contributes substantially to the overall poor prognosis of lung cancer despite apparently successful surgery.

Complete (R0) resection, defined as removal of all macroscopic tumor and microscopically negative margins, is considered the gold standard for localized disease (Sekihara et al. 2017). However, even after R0 resection, many patients experience relapse. In patients with resected early-stage non-small cell lung cancer, distant (metastatic) recurrence is the predominant pattern of relapse compared to local recurrence. Across large cohorts, approximately 50–82% of recurrences after complete resection occur at distant sites, such as the brain, bone, liver, adrenal glands, and contralateral lung, while local-only recurrence is less common, typically accounting for 13–25% of first failures (Potter et al. 2023).

This predominance of distant recurrence reflects the presence of micrometastatic disease, tumor cells that have disseminated prior to surgery but remain undetectable by conventional imaging or pathology. These micrometastases can remain dormant or proliferate after removal of the primary tumor, leading to metastatic relapse despite apparently curative resection (Demicheli et al. 2012). Clinicopathological factors such as lymphovascular invasion, nodal involvement, adenocarcinoma histology, and advanced stage are associated with a higher risk of distant recurrence and organ-specific metastatic patterns (Shimizu et al. 2020).

Reliance on standard postoperative surveillance using radiologic imaging, primarily contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) of the chest and occasionally positron emission tomography/computed tomography (PET/CT), delays the detection of recurrence in patients with resected early-stage non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) until disease burden becomes radiologically visible, thereby missing the window of minimal residual disease (MRD), when micrometastatic tumor cells are present but undetectable by imaging (Schneider et al. 2020).

CT-based follow-up is more sensitive than chest radiography for identifying asymptomatic recurrences and second primary lung cancers at an earlier, potentially treatable stage; however, this earlier detection does not consistently translate into improved overall survival, as demonstrated in the IFCT-

0302 randomized trial and other studies (Westeel et al. 2022). Current guidelines from the American Society of Clinical Oncology and the American College of Radiology recommend routine chest CT at 6–12-month intervals during the first two years and annually thereafter, while acknowledging that imaging cannot identify MRD and that most detected recurrences are already macroscopic (Madan et al. 2025).

PET/CT may improve sensitivity for certain metastatic sites but is not recommended for routine follow-up due to cost, radiation exposure, and lack of proven superiority over CT alone (Kaumanns et al. 2022). Furthermore, imaging modalities have limited ability to distinguish recurrence from post-surgical changes and may fail to detect small or hypometabolic lesions.

In summary, standard imaging-based follow-up is limited by its inability to detect MRD, resulting in delayed intervention until recurrence is radiologically apparent, which may compromise prognosis. Earlier detection strategies, such as ctDNA-based MRD assessment, are under investigation but not yet standard of care (Choi et al. 2011).

In this context, circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) and total circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) have emerged as promising minimally invasive biomarkers capable of detecting residual tumor activity earlier than imaging. ctDNA refers to DNA fragments shed from apoptotic or necrotic tumor cells into the bloodstream, constituting a fraction of the total cfDNA pool (Xia et al. 2022). Landmark studies in lung cancer, particularly the TRACERx initiative led by Abbosh et al., have demonstrated that postoperative ctDNA positivity predicts relapse months earlier than standard radiologic imaging: for example, in the TRACERx cohort, ctDNA detection preceded radiologic relapse by a median of 164 days (range 0–984) in preoperative shedders (Abbosh et al. 2023). Similarly, other analyses suggest that ctDNA can identify minimal residual disease and impending recurrence in resected NSCLC (Tian et al. 2024). Nevertheless, major guideline bodies such as the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) currently state that ctDNA for MRD detection in solid tumors remains investigational and is not yet recommended outside of clinical trials (Pascual et al. 2022).

In contrast to ctDNA, total circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) represents the entire pool of extracellular DNA fragments released into the bloodstream from both tumor and non-tumor sources, including apoptotic and necrotic cells. While ctDNA provides high tumor specificity through detection of somatic mutations, cfDNA reflects a broader biological signal that may be influenced by tumor burden, tissue injury, inflammation, and treatment-related effects. Studies have suggested that longitudinal changes in cfDNA concentration may correlate with disease dynamics and treatment response, although these signals are not tumor-specific (Pascual et al. 2022; Tan et al. 2024).

While mutation-specific ctDNA assays offer high specificity and sensitivity, requiring tumor sequencing and panel design, their implementation remains complex and costly (Tan et al. 2024). In contrast, monitoring total cfDNA dynamics (i.e., longitudinal changes in overall circulating DNA concentration) represents a more accessible surrogate approach for possible residual disease, especially in early-stage clinical settings where mutation tracking may not be feasible. Although cfDNA lacks the tumor specificity of ctDNA, changes in cfDNA levels may nonetheless reflect underlying tumor burden changes and offer a pragmatic option in pilot studies (Dao et al. 2023).

In this study, postoperative cfDNA kinetics in a cohort of surgically treated lung cancer patients was evaluated. The aims were to characterize the pattern of cfDNA decline or persistence after surgery and to assess associations between cfDNA dynamics, pathological stage (TNM), administration of adjuvant therapy, and early clinical outcome. By exploring whether an easily measurable biomarker could stratify patients at higher risk of relapse, this study aims to contribute to the development of molecular-based postoperative surveillance strategies in lung cancer.

Materials and methods

Study cohort

A total of 12 patients with histologically confirmed lung cancer who underwent curative-intent surgical resection were included in this observational pilot study. All patients were monitored prospectively using predefined postoperative cfDNA sampling intervals. Clinical information (TNM stage, tumor size, type of surgery, and outcome status) was extracted from medical records.

Sample collection and processing

Peripheral blood samples (4–6 mL) were collected at four predefined time points: preoperatively (T_0), postoperative day 10 (T_1), 1 month (T_2), and 3 months (T_3). All samples were drawn into Streck Cell-Free DNA BCT® tubes, ensuring stabilization of cfDNA and preventing leukocyte lysis during transport and processing.

Plasma was isolated using a double-centrifugation protocol ($1600 \times g$ for 10 min followed by $16,000 \times g$ for 10 min).

cfDNA extraction was performed using the TAN-Bead OptiPure cfDNA Kit (TANBead), optimized for extraction from plasma/serum, on the Maelstrom Switch 8 automated nucleic acid extraction system. The method is based on automated magnetic bead-based extraction, ensuring high purity, reproducibility, and minimal carryover of potential inhibitors.

cfDNA concentration was quantified using the DeNovix QFX Fluorometer (DeNovix Inc., USA) with a high-sensitivity dsDNA fluorescent assay, according to the manufacturer's instructions. This fluorometric method is based on fluorescent dyes that selectively bind to double-stranded

DNA, thereby minimizing the influence of contaminants such as proteins, salts, or free nucleotides.

Spectrophotometric analysis was additionally performed using the NanoDrop One Spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) as a supplementary quality-control step to assess nucleic acid purity using A260/A280 and A260/A230 ratios. However, final cfDNA quantification was based exclusively on fluorometric measurements because of their superior specificity and accuracy in low-concentration DNA samples. All measurements were performed in technical duplicates, and mean values were used for downstream analysis.

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables were summarized as means and standard deviations.

Changes in cfDNA concentration across time points were evaluated descriptively and by within-subject trend inspection.

To assess the prognostic value of cfDNA levels, patients were categorized according to their survival status at last follow-up (alive vs. deceased). Between-group comparisons of cfDNA levels at individual time points were performed using Welch's *t*-test, which is equivalent to one-way ANOVA for unequal variances. For completeness, ANOVA *F*-statistics were also reported.

To explore the relationship between cfDNA persistence and outcome, simple linear regression was fitted with survival status as the dependent variable (0 = deceased, 1 = alive) and 3-month cfDNA levels as the predictor. The model served as an exploratory estimate of effect size given the small number of events.

Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$, but due to the pilot nature of the study, emphasis was placed on biological trends and effect sizes rather than formal hypothesis testing.

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of MU–Plovdiv (Protocol No. 9/28.11.2024; approval date: 11.12.2024). All participants provided informed consent.

Results

Individual cfDNA concentration values for all 12 patients across all time points are provided in Table 1.

Overall postoperative cfDNA dynamics

Longitudinal monitoring across the four postoperative time points revealed two distinct molecular trajectories.

The majority of patients (10/12; 83.3%) demonstrated a progressive decrease in cfDNA concentrations from T_0 to T_3 , consistent with effective surgical clearance of tumor burden.

In contrast, two patients (16.7%) showed persistent or rising cfDNA levels, failing to achieve molecular clearance during follow-up. Both patients subsequently died, constituting the entire mortality group.

This divergence in cfDNA kinetics suggests the presence of distinct molecular patterns. A favorable trend was

Table 1. Individual circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) concentration values measured at four time points in all 12 patients included in the study. T0 – preoperative baseline; T1 – day 10 after surgery; T2 – 1 month after surgery; T3 – 3 months after surgery.

Patient ID	Outcome	T0 (ng/ μ L)	T1 (ng/ μ L)	T2 (ng/ μ L)	T3 (ng/ μ L)
P1	Alive	1.6295	0.2791	0.2759	0.1944
P2	Alive	0.4143	0.4097	0.4011	0.2175
P3	Alive	0.6161	0.4104	0.1627	0.1591
P4	Alive	0.2930	0.2866	0.2841	0.2674
P5	Alive	0.3035	0.2737	0.2721	0.2719
P6	Alive	0.7761	0.3818	0.3816	0.3067
P7	Alive	0.3512	0.3466	0.2772	0.2569
P8	Alive	0.2499	0.2365	0.2289	0.2201
P9	Alive	0.3154	0.2814	0.2632	0.2457
P10	Alive	0.2241	0.2094	0.1957	0.1852
P11	Deceased	0.2745	0.2728	0.2727	0.2719
P12	Deceased	0.3351	0.3124	0.2998	0.2923

observed in all surviving patients, whereas persistent cfDNA levels were observed in both patients with fatal outcomes. However, variability between individual trajectories was also present.

Comparison of cfDNA concentrations by survival status

At the 3-month time point, surviving patients had significantly lower cfDNA levels compared to those who died:

- Survivors: mean = 0.2325 ng/ μ L, SD = 0.0453
- Deceased: mean = 0.2821 ng/ μ L, SD = 0.0144

Welch's *t*-test demonstrated a statistically significant difference:

- $t = -2.82$, $df \approx 10$, $p = 0.029$

The equivalent one-way ANOVA yielded:

- $F(1,10) = 7.95$, $p < 0.05$

No significant differences were observed at earlier time points (T0, T1, T2), supporting the hypothesis that molecular divergence emerges around or after the first postoperative month, when minimal residual disease becomes biologically active.

Linear regression analysis

A simple linear regression model (outcome ~ cfDNA at 3 months) demonstrated a negative association between cfDNA levels and probability of survival ($\beta = -3.62$, $R^2 = 0.18$). However, this association did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.17$).

Given the small sample size and limited number of events, this analysis should be considered exploratory, and no conclusions regarding predictive or prognostic value can be drawn.

Longitudinal cfDNA concentrations measured at four time points (T0–T3) for all patients. The main plot shows the full range of cfDNA values starting from 0 ng/ μ L. The inset provides a zoomed view of the 0.2–0.4 ng/ μ L range to improve visualization of interindividual differences. Solid lines represent surviving patients, while dashed lines represent deceased patients (Fig. 1).

At 3 months, cfDNA levels differed significantly between survivors and deceased patients (Fig. 2).

Discussion

The results of this pilot study support the emerging role of postoperative circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) dynamics as an early molecular indicator of minimal residual disease (MRD) and recurrence risk in surgically treated non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Longitudinal cfDNA monitoring revealed two distinct molecular trajectories: most patients demonstrated progressive cfDNA clearance consistent with effective surgical eradication, while a minority exhibited persistent or rising cfDNA levels, correlating with subsequent mortality. This dichotomy aligns with recent studies showing that persistent or rising ctDNA/cfDNA postoperatively has been associated with increased risk of relapse and inferior survival (Xia et al. 2022; Rosenlund et al. 2025).

In this cohort, cfDNA levels measured immediately after surgery (day 10 and 1 month) showed limited prognostic value, whereas the 3-month cfDNA level was both clinically and statistically informative. The timing of circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) measurement after surgery critically affects its prognostic value for minimal residual disease (MRD) in lung cancer patients. Measurements taken in the immediate postoperative period (day 10 or 1 month) are confounded by non-tumor-related cfDNA released due to surgical trauma, inflammation, and tissue repair, which can obscure tumor-specific signals and limit prognostic accuracy (Chen et al. 2019). Early postoperative cfDNA levels may reflect transient biological noise rather than true MRD status.

cfDNA levels at 3 months postoperatively provide more clinically and statistically informative results compared to earlier time points because, by this time, the confounding effects of surgery and inflammation have subsided, allowing persistent or rising cfDNA to more accurately reflect ongoing tumor activity and MRD (Zhao et al. 2021). Multiple studies demonstrate that cfDNA or ctDNA positivity at 3 months has been associated with increased risk of recurrence and mortality, with higher sensitivity and specificity for predicting outcomes than earlier measurements (Li et al. 2022; Tan et al. 2024; Xia et al. 2025). This delayed molecular divergence aligns with the biological latency of MRD regrowth and the kinetics of cfDNA clearance, making the 3-month time point optimal for risk stratification and guiding postoperative management.

Statistical analysis further supports this concept. The significant difference in 3-month cfDNA levels between survivors and deceased patients ($p = 0.029$) and the moderate

Figure 1. Longitudinal cfDNA concentrations measured at four time points (T0–T3) for all patients. The main plot shows the full range of cfDNA values starting from 0 ng/μL. The inset provides a zoomed view of the 0.2–0.4 ng/μL range to improve visualization of interindividual differences. Solid lines represent surviving patients, while dashed lines represent deceased patients.

Figure 2. cfDNA levels at 3 months differed significantly between survivors and deceased patients.

negative correlation with outcome ($r = -0.42$) indicate that cfDNA trend monitoring may offer early prognostic insight even in small, heterogeneous patient groups. Although the regression analysis suggested a negative association between cfDNA levels at 3 months and survival outcome, this relationship did not reach statistical significance. Therefore, these findings should be interpreted with caution and considered exploratory. No definitive conclusions regarding prognostic or predictive value can be drawn from this dataset.

The lack of statistical significance is likely attributable to the small number of events (2/12), which limits the statistical power of the analysis.

Importantly, the two patients with persistent cfDNA elevations also had more advanced pathological stages (N involvement or larger tumor burden), reinforcing the relationship between biological aggressiveness and molecular non-clearance. Meanwhile, several patients receiving adjuvant therapy exhibited more pronounced cfDNA declines, supporting the hypothesis that cfDNA may serve as a useful early marker of treatment response.

Recent prospective trials have demonstrated that patients with persistent cfDNA/ctDNA positivity after surgery derive significant benefit from adjuvant systemic therapy, with substantially improved recurrence-free survival com-

pared to MRD-positive patients who do not receive adjuvant treatment (Xia et al. 2022). Conversely, MRD-negative patients do not benefit from adjuvant therapy and may be exposed to unnecessary toxicity if treated empirically (Xia et al. 2022). Dynamic cfDNA/ctDNA monitoring during adjuvant therapy further refines risk stratification: clearance of molecular disease correlates with favorable therapeutic response and improved clinical outcomes, while persistent ctDNA identifies patients at continued risk of relapse despite therapy. This growing body of evidence highlights the potential for MRD-guided escalation and de-escalation strategies in postoperative management.

While these findings highlight the potential of cfDNA monitoring in postoperative lung cancer care, several limitations must be acknowledged. The sample size was small ($n = 12$), and only two mortality events occurred, precluding robust survival modeling such as Kaplan–Meier or Cox regression. Additionally, cfDNA quantification without mutation-specific ctDNA assays cannot distinguish tumor-derived fragments from background cfDNA originating from normal tissues. Future work incorporating personalized ctDNA mutation tracking, digital PCR, or targeted NGS panels is expected to significantly improve sensitivity and specificity.

Nevertheless, even with these limitations, the consistency of the cfDNA trend patterns, the clear separation between survivors and deceased patients, and the alignment of these findings with established MRD literature suggest that postoperative cfDNA kinetic profiling is a feasible and promising strategy for improving risk stratification after lung cancer surgery. Larger prospective cohorts with mutation-informed ctDNA assays and detailed time-to-event data will be essential to validate these preliminary observations and assess the clinical utility of integrating cfDNA MRD monitoring into postoperative surveillance algorithms.

Conclusion

This pilot study demonstrates that postoperative monitoring of circulating cell-free DNA (cfDNA) is a feasible approach for evaluating molecular changes following curative-intent surgery in patients with lung cancer.

In this cohort, differences in cfDNA dynamics between patients with favorable and unfavorable outcomes were observed; however, variability and partial overlap between individual trajectories were also present, limiting their interpretability at the individual level.

Emerging evidence from larger studies suggests that circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA)-based minimal residual disease assessment may have clinical utility in guiding postoperative management. However, given the methodological differences and the limited size of the present cfDNA-based cohort, such implications cannot be directly extrapolated from the present findings.

Although postoperative cfDNA dynamics may reflect underlying biological processes related to minimal residual disease, the present findings are based on a small cohort and should be interpreted as hypothesis-generating. No defini-

tive conclusions regarding prognostic value can be drawn, and validation in larger prospective studies is required.

Acknowledgements

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and Good Clinical Practice guidelines. Ethical approval was obtained from the Scientific Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Plovdiv (Protocol No. 9/28.11.2024; approval date: 11.12.2024). All procedures complied with national regulations for clinical and scientific research involving human participants.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The declarations of informed consent are deposited at the Department of Special Surgery, Medical University of Plovdiv, where the surgical procedures and patient recruitment were performed.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

Project No. 3.4.18, "ctDNA as a Biomarker for Early Diagnosis and Monitoring of Patients with Lung Carcinoma" – a project related to applied research aimed at innovation or intellectual property and implemented under Contract No. BG-RRP-2.004-0007-C01, "Programme for Strategic Research and Innovation for the Development of MU–Plovdiv (PSRI-MUP)," Pillar 2: Establishment of a Network of Research Universities of the Programme for Accelerating Economic Recovery and Transformation through Science and Innovation, from Component "Innovative Bulgaria" of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan.

Author contributions

H. Ivanov conceived and designed the study, supervised the project, contributed to data interpretation, performed statistical analysis, and drafted the manuscript. V. Stoyano-

va contributed to study design, and critical revision of the manuscript. A. Linev participated in sample processing, cfDNA extraction and quantification, and data acquisition. I. Pochileev contributed to laboratory methodology, quality control, and data curation. A. Kulenska was responsible for surgical data collection and clinical follow-up of patients. A. Chapkanov contributed to clinical data interpretation and correlation with pathological and surgical findings. R. Dimov participated in patient management, clinical outcome assessment, and manuscript review.

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Author ORCIDs

Hristo Ivanov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7912-3673>

Vili Stoyanova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6758-7964>

Iliyan Pochileev <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8445-2583>

Antoaneta Chirlova-Kulenska <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7768-1109>

Rosen Dimov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5915-4846>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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